

A study examines the importance of classroom assessment in teaching learning process in government secondary schools of district Naseerabad Baluchistan, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: This main objective of this research examines the importance of classroom assessment in teaching learning process in government secondary schools of district Naseerabad Baluchistan, Pakistan. Researcher conducted the mixed-method research, qualitative and quantitative, quantitative research was used survey questionnaire by 5point Likert scale and questionnaire was adapted and qualitative research was used through semi-stature interview. Researcher was used the thematic analysis. Study was conducted in District Naseerabad, Baluchistan Pakistan, research was based on convening sampling; 201 students were selected and 20 principals and teachers were filled google foam and face to face interview. Quantitative results analyzed through percentage and qualitative data analyzed through thematic analysis. Finding of the study, research aimed to measure the participants' belief in the importance of assessment in the teaching and learning process, the positive responses indicate that teachers and students recognize the dynamic role that assessment plays in gauging learning outcomes and driving the educational process. Principals believe that every teacher uses various assessment strategies to evaluate and enhance the teaching learning process like observation, teachers observe students in the classroom to gauge their engagement, participation, and understanding ongoing assessments during the learning process such as quizzes, class discussion, and providing timely feedback to students. It is based on established educational theory emphasizing the significance of assessment for tracking progress and improving learning.

Keywords: Assessment, Learning Process, Teaching Methods and Learning Behaviors

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1. Introduction

Assessment plays a pivotal role in the realm of education, serving as a fundamental component of the instructional process. Its primary function is to gauge and evaluate whether the predefined objectives and goals of education are effectively being achieved. In essence, assessment acts as the compass that guides educational progress (Council, 2001). This research embarks on a critical examination of the importance of assessment in secondary-level government schools in Baluchistan, Pakistan, with a focus on its multifaceted impact on students, teachers, and the overall educational landscape (Sain, 2023). The significance of secondary education cannot be overstated, as it bridges the gap between foundational learning and specialized knowledge, preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of adulthood. Naseerabad, a region marked by its diverse population and distinct educational needs, presents a compelling backdrop for this study. Similarly, Government schools, as the primary providers of secondary education, are entrusted with the task of equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for future success (John-Nelson, 2020).

Assessment methods in these schools have a profound influence on the quality of education delivered and the outcomes achieved (Biggs, Tang, & Kennedy, 2022). They serve as the linchpin in the educational process, guiding curriculum development, instructional strategies, and individualized support for students. In a time when educational systems worldwide are experiencing transformative shifts, Naseerabad's government schools face unique challenges and opportunities in their pursuit of excellence.

Role of Government institutions in assessment process

Government institutions play a fundamental role in the functioning of any society. They are responsible for delivering essential services, implementing policies, and upholding the rule of law. To ensure the effective operation of these institutions, assessment and evaluation are indispensable tools (Khan, 1998). In education, the term appraisal alludes to the wide assortment of strategies that teachers use to assess, measure, and report the scholarly availability, learning progress, and expertise securing of understudies from preschool through school and adulthood. It is the course of methodically gathering data as a component of an assessment (Council, 2001). Assessment is carried out to see what children and young people know, understand and are able to do (Lefevre, 2010).

Assessment in education is the collation of various data from different resources to check the student's learning and understanding (Longhurst et al., 2020). This data aids in assessing student progress and obstacles when viewed and contextualized. It can additionally give an understanding into the motivations behind why understudies deal with the issues they face and can assist with overcoming any barrier between satisfied maintenance and better understudy execution (Sundaram, Ramesh, & ISSN, 2022).

Assessment as aspect of education and professional development

“The word assess comes from the Latin word *assidere* which means to sit beside (Brainard, Goodwin, & children, 1997). Literally than, to assess means to sit beside the learner” Furthermore Assessment is a crucial aspect of education and professional development, serving as a means to measure and evaluate individuals' knowledge, skills, and abilities in various contexts (Loacker, 1985). However, in education assessment is a fundamental and multifaceted concept that plays a crucial role in shaping the learning experience of students across different age groups and educational levels. It encompasses a wide array of methods and practices aimed at evaluating, measuring, and documenting various aspects of students' academic readiness, learning progress, and skill acquisition. These assessments are conducted from the early stages of preschool education all the way through college and into adulthood. It the process of evaluating or evaluate something to gain a better understanding of its quality, value, or performance (Sihotang, Utari, & Sihotang, 2022).

Assessment is a multifaceted process

Assessment is a multifaceted process integral to education that serves various essential functions. At its core, assessment is the systematic and organized approach of gathering information and data about students' learning and development. It involves a series of steps, each contributing to a comprehensive understanding of students' progress and abilities (Holmboe et al., 2010).

Selecting Assessment Methods

Once the goals are established, educators must choose appropriate assessment methods. These can include tests, quizzes, projects, presentations, observations, and more. The selection depends on what aspect of learning is being evaluated and the students' age and abilities (Genesee & Hamayan, 1994).

Designing Assessment Tools

Designing assessment tools involves creating the actual instruments or tasks that students will engage with. This could entail drafting test questions, rubrics for grading assignments, or creating specific criteria for evaluating projects (Colton & Covert, 2007). And the other hand, collecting data in this stage, students participate in the assessment, and their responses or performances are recorded. This step can take various forms, such as conducting exams, reviewing assignments, or observing student interactions (Hsia, Huang, & Hwang, 2016). After data collection, educators analyze the information to gain insights into students' performance. This analysis often involves statistical techniques and can provide valuable information about individual and group achievements (Zhang et al., 2022). Interpreting assessment results involves understanding what the data signifies. Educators assess whether students have met the learning objectives, identified strengths and weaknesses, and determined areas for improvement. Providing Feedback Assessments serve as a means of giving students constructive feedback about their progress. This feedback helps them understand their errors and where they can improve. It also facilitates self-reflection and self-regulation in the learning process (Clark, 2012). Furthermore; Using assessment data, the insights gained from assessments are not solely for grading purposes. They are used to inform instructional decisions. Teachers can adapt their teaching methods based on the assessment results to better meet students' needs (Brink, Bartz, & Evaluation, 2019). Supporting Learning Assessments are not just a one-time event, they can be used formatively, providing ongoing feedback to support student learning. This can involve re-teaching certain concepts or offering additional resources for struggling students. Improving Performance Assessments often offer students an opportunity to assimilate new information and make improvements. For example, if a

student receives feedback on a test, they can use that feedback to study more effectively and perform better on the next assessment (Marzano, Pickering, & McTighe, 1993).

Objectives of the study

1. To analyze the role of assessment in teaching learning process.
2. To explore the use of assessment techniques in classroom.
3. To highlight issues that affect student learning.
4. To discuss the role of assessment in teaching learning process in Government Secondary schools Baluchistan Pakistan.

Research questions

1. Why assessment is important during teaching learning process?
2. How to know about the use of assessment techniques in classroom?
3. How to highlight the issue that affect student learning?
4. Why discuss the role of assessment in teaching learning process in Government Secondary schools Baluchistan Pakistan?

2. Theoretical background of the study

The theoretical framework for this study was grounded in educational theories such as constructivism, formative assessment, and assessment for learning. Constructivism emphasizes that students construct their knowledge through active engagement with learning materials and social interactions (Mohammed & Kinyó, 2020). Formative assessment focuses on using assessment as a tool for ongoing feedback and improvement, rather than just a measure of achievement (Clark, 2012).

Assessment for learning emphasizes the importance of involving students in the assessment process to enhance their learning and met cognitive skills (William & Thompson, 2017). These theories were guided the exploration of the importance of assessment in secondary level government schools and its impact on student learning.

On the most effective ways to evaluate the learning outcomes of students, educators have differing viewpoints (Marzano et al., 1993).

The Significance of Classroom Environment Assessment

A well-structured classroom environment can significantly impact students' academic achievements, motivation, and overall well-being (Thoonen, Slegers, Peetsma, & Oort, 2011). Hence, assessing and improving the classroom environment is of paramount importance. The physical classroom environment is the most tangible aspect of assessment (Han, Moon, Lee, & journal, 2019). Factors such as seating arrangement, lighting, temperature, and classroom design can significantly influence students' comfort and concentration (Ramli, Zain, Campus, Chepa, & Bharu, 2018). For instance, suggests that classroom design can impact student engagement and learning outcomes. A well-ventilated, well-lit, and organized classroom can enhance students' focus and productivity (Sanders, 2013).

Methods of Classroom Environment Assessment

Classroom observations by educators or trained observers can provide valuable insights into the physical, social, and emotional aspects of the classroom environment (Pianta, La Paro, & Hamre, 2008). These observations can be supplemented with checklists or rubrics to ensure consistency in assessment. Gathering feedback from students, parents, and teachers through surveys and questionnaires can provide a holistic view of the classroom environment (Fraser, 2012). Questions can be tailored to assess various aspects, including teacher-student relationships, peer interactions, and physical comfort.

Teachers can also self-assess their classroom environments by reflecting on their teaching practices and interactions with students (Brophy & issues, 2006). Self-assessment encourages educators to continually improve their teaching strategies and classroom management.

Assessments can reveal areas in need of improvement. For instance, if the assessment identifies poor student-teacher relationships, targeted professional development can be provided to enhance educators' interpersonal skills (Stough & Montague, 2014).

Assessing the classroom environment can highlight potential barriers to inclusion for students with disabilities or diverse backgrounds. This knowledge can drive efforts to create more inclusive learning environments (Elvey & Burke, 2023). Sharing assessment results with parents can promote collaborative efforts to create a conducive classroom environment (Henderson, Carson, Avallone, & Whipple, 2011). Parents can provide valuable insights into students' needs and expectations.

Study Framework

Assessment practices in education are guided by various theoretical frameworks. One widely accepted framework is the constructivist approach, which posits that learning is an active process, and assessment should be designed to measure students' understanding, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking skills ((Biggs, Tang, & Instruction, 2011). In Naseerabad, the application of this framework is crucial in fostering deeper learning and preparing students for real-world challenges. The independent variable; The role of assessment in teaching and sub factors are; check issue that affects students learning, teachers used assessment tools in classroom. Dependent variable; Innovative assessment in teaching learning process and impact on assessment techniques in student learning out comes.

Figure 1

3. Research methodology

Methods

Researcher conducted the mix-method research, qualitative and quantitative, quantitative research was used survey questionnaire by 5point Likert scale and questionnaire was adapted (Fluit, Bolhuis, Grol, Laan, & Wensing, 2010). Survey research is defined as "the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions" (Ponto, 2015). This kind of examination considers different strategies to enlist members, gather information, and use different techniques for instrumentation. Study examination can utilize quantitative exploration methodologies (e.g., utilizing surveys with mathematically appraised things), subjective exploration techniques (e.g., utilizing unassuming inquiries), or the two systems (i.e., blended strategies). As it is

frequently used to portray and investigate human way of behaving, overviews are subsequently every now and again utilized in friendly and mental exploration (Singleton Jr & Straits, 2012). and qualitative research was used through semi-structure interview. Researcher used the thematic analysis, for the reason that of its simple yet assuming data analysis process can be shown within together types of research paradigms (O’Mahoney, 2012) and Constructionist paradigm (Moller, Clarke, Braun, Tischner, & Vossler, 2021).

Sample size

Study was conducted in District Naseerabad, Baluchistan Pakistan. Researcher used the convening sampling; 201 students were selected and 20 teachers were filled google foam and face to face interview. Quantitative results analyzed through percentage and qualitative data analyzed through thematic analysis.

4. Results

Analyze the role of assessment in teaching learning process and highlight the issue that affect students learning

Figure.1

In this table researcher was collect the data to different levels students of District Naseerabad. Question one I believe that assessment play vital role in teaching learning process. to response of strongly agree are 94%, agree respondent are 4% neutral 1% disagree 0.5% and strongly disagree is 0.5%.

Figure 1

Above table mentioned that the in-teaching learning process, I prepare my salve regularly for assessment According to type of quantitative research, researcher was collected the data through google form, there were responses strongly agree 60.2%, agree response are 31.8%, neutral 7%, disagree is 0%, and strongly disagree is 1%. Data was supporting the positive result regarding this study.

Figure 2

Question three researcher was collected the data on the given question Students enjoy to solve the given task of assessment and it results shows the positive response responses strongly agree was 60.2% agree responses 30.8%, neutral 8%, disagree 1% and strongly disagree was 0%

Figure 4

Researcher was collected the data through quantitative method and used online questioner form to get result. Question four Through assessment I feel that my selves making progress in this subject. Researcher was collecting the data it indicates the positive response strongly agree 58.2%, agree was

29.4%, neutral 9%, disagree 2.5%, and strongly disagree 0.9%.

Figure 5

Question five My teacher available for students who may be facing personal or academic challenges and support them, the above chart shows the response it was strongly agree 46.3%, agree 33.8%, neutral 7%, disagree 8% and strongly disagree was 5%.

Figure 6

Question six, I feel that my teacher values every student's input and opinions in the classroom. strongly agree respondent was 47.8%, agree 28.9%, neutral 15.9%, disagree 4.5% and strongly disagree was 2.9%.

Figure 7

Last question researcher was found the result on that question. Sometimes I experience issues related to bullying but our teacher manages it effectively the results show positive response the strongly agree response 41.8%, agree 30.3% neutral 15.9%, disagree 6.5% and strongly agree 5.5%.

Qualitative data collected from Teachers and discuss the role of assessment in teaching learning process in government boys' high schools

Researcher explained given statement that refers to the thematic analysis given by (Crosswell & Beutel, 2017) data collected from the teachers of Government secondary schools through the conducted semi structure interview.

Importance of teaching learning process

The teaching learning process is of great importance because it is the foundation of education and the transfer of knowledge and skills from educators to learners, fostering intellectual and personal growth enhance critical thinking, problem solving abilities and other competencies essential for personal and professional success.

Discuss the (teacher use the strategies) assessment of teaching learning process

I believe that every teacher uses various assessment strategies to evaluate and enhance the teaching learning process like Observation teachers observe students in the classroom to gauge their engagement, participation, and understanding ongoing assessments during the learning process such as quizzes, class discussion, and providing timely feedback to students.

Resolve the issue related to teaching learning process

According to my point of view resolve the issue related to teaching learning process can be complex as vary widely based on specific circumstances but it can address effectively through communication and listen actively to concerns and feedback offer support services for students these steps resolve the issues and head teacher should provide teacher training and professional development opportunities for teachers to improve

their teaching methods and strategies to use student centered approaches, create collaboration environment and stay informed about current educational research and innovation practices.

Highlights the recommendations to betterment of teaching learning process

As a teacher I recommend that government teacher should encourage active participation and engagement in the learning process through discussions, group activities and more focus to student's individuals needs and to change teaching styles and build interests to make learning more relevant and engaging.

5. Findings

The findings of this thesis study reveal the importance of assessment in secondary-level government schools of district Naseerabad. The data collected from the survey responses showed that the majority of participants had a positive view of assessment in the teaching and learning process.

6. Discussions

Assessment's vital role, the first question aimed to gauge the participants' belief in the importance of assessment in the teaching and learning process. The positive responses indicate that teachers and students recognize the vital role that assessment plays in gauging learning outcomes and driving the educational process. This aligns with the established educational theory emphasizing the significance of assessment for tracking progress and improving learning.

Regular Preparation for Assessment The second question explored how well-prepared students are for assessments. The positive responses suggest that students are actively engaged in preparing for assessments, which is crucial for a productive learning environment. Enjoyment in Assessment Tasks Question three inquired about students' enjoyment in solving assessment tasks. The fact that students reported enjoying assessment tasks is promising, as it can contribute to a positive learning atmosphere and increased motivation for learning. Comfort in Seeking Clarification The fourth question assessed students' comfort in asking questions or seeking clarification from their teachers. Positive responses suggest that students feel supported in their learning, which is essential for a healthy student-teacher relationship and effective learning. Feedback on Assignments and Assessments The fifth question focused on the feedback students receive on their assignments and assessments. Positive responses indicate that feedback mechanisms are in place, which is essential for helping students understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Sense of Progress Through Assessment Question six examined whether students feel that they are making progress in subjects through assessment. Positive responses suggest that assessment is seen as a tool for measuring and facilitating progress, motivating students to perform better. Peer Assessment and Group Projects The seventh question explored whether teachers involve students in peer assessments or group projects. Positive responses indicate that teachers are implementing active learning strategies, fostering collaboration and critical thinking. Teacher Support for Personal and Academic Challenges Question eight addressed the availability of teachers to support students facing personal or academic challenges. Positive responses indicate that teachers are actively engaged in supporting students' well-being, which is crucial for a holistic educational experience. Valuing Student Input and Opinions The ninth question sought to understand whether students feel that their teachers value their input and opinions. Positive responses suggest that students perceive an inclusive classroom environment where their

voices are valued. Effective Management of Bullying The final question explored how effectively teachers manage issues related to bullying. Positive responses indicate that teachers are proactive in creating a safe and respectful learning environment.

7. Recommendation

Based on these findings, it is recommended that the district Naseerabad's secondary-level government schools continue to prioritize assessment in the teaching and learning process. Additionally, educators should consider further enhancing peer assessments, encouraging active student participation, and maintaining open channels of communication.

1. Improving Assessment Practices Propose recommendations for enhancing assessment methods and practices. Consider factors like alignment with learning objectives, diversity of assessment types, and timely feedback.
2. Professional Development Suggest recommendations for teacher training and professional development related to assessment.
3. Student involvement in Assessment propose ways to involve students in the assessment process, promoting self-assessment and peer assessment
4. Policy and Curriculum Changes Address the need for policy changes and curriculum adjustments to support effective assessment practices.
5. Encouraging the use of a variety of assessment methods to create to diverse learning styles.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the importance of assessment in secondary-level Government schools of district Naseerabad is evident through the positive responses collected in this study. Assessment plays a crucial role in fostering a conducive learning environment, motivating students, and ensuring their overall well-being. These findings highlight the need for continued emphasis on effective assessment practices in the education system, with the potential to enhance the overall quality of education and the teacher education is a dynamic field that requires ongoing assessment and improvement to meet the ever-evolving demands of education. Addressing challenges such as recruitment, diversity, and technological integration while embracing evidence-based practices and collaborative partnerships can lead to more effective teacher preparation. The quality of teacher education directly impacts the quality of education that students receive, making it a critical area of focus for educational institutions and policymakers in the district Naseerabad further more Assessment is a cornerstone of effective governance in government institutions. It ensures accountability by holding public officials responsible for their actions, promotes efficiency by identifying areas for improvement, and builds public trust by fostering transparency. While challenges such as data quality and political interference exist, the importance of assessment in government cannot be overstated. To maintain the integrity of government institutions and serve the best interests of the public, ongoing and robust assessment mechanisms must be prioritized. Ultimately, the success of government institutions hinges on their ability to be transparent, accountable, and efficient, and assessment is the tool that makes this possible.

9. Acknowledgment

Author thankful to the principals from the schools which this data was collected, especially thanks to students, who filled my questionnaire and responded so well, as a

researcher, have tried to fill only few components that are the role of assessment in teaching methods and teaching learning process, the rest of its impacts remain, due to lack of time and etc.

10. Future Research

this research examines the importance of classroom assessment in teaching learning process in government secondary schools of district Naseerabad Baluchistan, Pakistan but due to short of time, the influence of teaching methods on assessment was not checked. In future research, these methods can be checked.

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